

early growth of rice (land not flooded), when VAM fungi are colonizing young plants not yet fully established. It is possible that older, established rice plants in flooded fields may show a different response to VAM fungal colonization.

In all cases where nutrients were supplied, colonization of rice roots was significantly lower than that in roots of plants supplied with deionized water. It is

possible that higher availability of nutrients to plant roots depressed VAM fungal colonization. Other studies have suggested this depression in colonization may be due to the reduction of exudate leakage and/or the greater availability of inorganic nutrients in the rhizosphere.

The high biomass of plants in the deionized water treatment may be due to

higher VAM fungal colonization in this treatment.

This study suggests that VAM fungi may have a detrimental effect on early growth of rice, reducing establishment. This relationship may change as rice plants grow and become better established. The significance of the roles of VAM fungi and inorganic fertilizer needs further investigation. ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effects of paclobutrazol and KH_2PO_4 on rice seedlings and grain yield

Guang Jian Liang, Biology Department, Xijiang University, Zhaoqing, P.O. Box 526061, China

Paclobutrazol (Pac) treatment reduces rice seedling height in summer and lodging in autumn, but does not significantly increase yields.

We evaluated the effect on yield of applying Pac alone and in a mixture with KH_2PO_4 to rice seedlings. All treated plants were shorter, had wider seedling base, and more tillers than untreated controls.

Pac alone did not increase the height of the first tiller, production of new roots after transplanting, yield components, or yield. Pac plus KH_2PO_4 , however, increased first tiller height and new root

Table 1. Effect of paclobutrazol and KH_2PO_4 application on rice seedlings. Zhaoqing, China, 1988-89 early season.

Treatment	Seedlings		Tillers (no./seedling)	1st tiller length (cm)	New roots ^a (no./plant)
	Height (cm)	Base width (mm)			
	<i>Shan You 2</i>				
Control	32	4.0	0.6	15.0	3
270 ppm Pac	27	4.5	2.0	17.5	4
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	29	5.8	2.5	22.0	5
LSD (P = 0.05)	2	0.6	1.1	3.0	2
	<i>Shan You 63</i>				
Control	28	3.6	2.3	11.5	4
270 ppm Pac	24	4.5	3.0	12.5	5
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	25	5.4	3.8	19.2	7
LSD (P = 0.05)	2	0.6	1.0	3.0	2

^a Measured 5 d after transplanting.

Table 2. Effect of paclobutrazol and KH_2PO_4 application on grain yield and yield components.^a Zhaoqing, China, 1988-89 late season.^a

Treatment	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
	<i>Shan You 2</i>			
Control	297	106	27.0	8.5
270 ppm Pac	296	105	27.6	8.6
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	306	108	28.0	9.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	7.5	4.0	0.9	0.4
	<i>Shan You 63</i>			
Control	292	116	28.1	9.5
270 ppm Pac	295	114	28.2	9.2
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	300	122	29.0	10.6
LSD (P = 0.05)	7.8	4.2	0.8	0.4

Fertilized with 225 kg N, 66 kg P, 149 kg K/ha.

number (Table 1), thereby increasing the capacity for absorption of mineral nutrients.

As a result, panicle number, filled grain number, and 1,000-grain weight increased.

Shan You 63 yielded 10.6 t/ha in the late season (Table 2), a new record in a 200,000-ha area of Zhaoqing. ■

Fertilizer management

Effect of straw + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ application on rice

Jian Luo and Zhi-wu Huang, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, China

We studied the influence of C:N ratio and preflooding on rice growth and production when rice straw was applied with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ in a greenhouse pot experiment, 1988 late season.

Pearl River alluvial soil (medium loam, pH 6.5, 0.15% total N, 2.5% organic C, CEC 14 meq/100 g soil) was air dried and screened, and placed in pottery pots at 5 kg/pot. Superphosphate (5.0 g/pot) and KCl (2.0 g/pot) were basally applied. Rice straw (0.72% total N, C:N ratio 53) of 0, 9.8, 37.3, and 127.1 g, respectively, needed to establish 0, 10, 25, or 40 C:N ratio was thoroughly mixed with the soil. N (300 mg) as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solution was banded 5 cm deep into each pot in an 8-cm-diameter circle. The pots were preflooded at 2, 4, or 6 wk, and 9 seedlings/pot transplanted. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design.

Preflooding had no significant effects on tiller number, panicle dry weight, or